

FEATURES OF THE USE OF YOUTH SLANG

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the study of the use of youth slang, its influence on oral and written speech (based on the results of a sociological study). About the influence of social networks on the formation of the speech of the younger generation.

Keywords: Internet, youth, slang, society, statistics, emoticons, intonation, emotions.

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

Young people spend most of their time on the Internet. They are the inheritors of the material and spiritual wealth of society, and they are the main driving force and transformative force of society. The data of sociological studies prove the fact that the main Internet users are young people.

Thus, according to the All-Russian Center for the Study of Public Opinion (ARCSPO), about 90% of the surveyed young people aged 18 to 24 go online every day. More than half of citizens (64%) use the Internet to communicate with relatives and friends. The global network is gradually replacing personal communication, and it has become indirect.

People meet less and less often and spend less and less time together, but they spend more and more time on the Internet, and the communication process is almost always carried out there. If we look at online communication, we will find that this is not the usual process of transmitting information that we are used to. Internet voice has the following characteristics :

1. Communication should be short and effective ;
2. Punctuation marks are smoothed for fast transmission of information ;
3. The transmission of intonation and emotions is carried out with the help of "emoticons" (special symbols designed to convey emotions and feelings).

The objects of research are young people, and the objects of research are:

- Features of the structure of speech and vocabulary of young people in online communication.

-To find out what the structure of speech in virtual communication is, we chose two methods - sociological experiments and semi-official interviews.

In both cases, the samples were spontaneous, they were interviewed and accepted the respondents who participated in the experiment were the most accessible. Its purpose is to identify the reaction of young people to written literary speeches written for them and to show that online speech is a new form of language. It exists in written form, but it complies with the rules not of written speech, but oral.

The essence of the experiment is as follows: the subject received a message written in literary language on the social network Facebook. In the received message, we observed in which language the interlocutor would answer us, and checked according to the following criteria:

1. The volume of the message (response) ;
2. "Emoticons" and the presence of punctuation marks ;
3. Narrative language (literary, non-literary) ;
4. Is there any fragment in the message (the answer is not solid, but is broken into several staccato phrases).

A preliminary guide with a list of questions was compiled for the interview. Using this method, we want to understand the form of Internet communication, the structure of the words used, which words are used, frequency and purpose, as well as whether the interviewee uses online slang other than virtual in real communication. Therefore, judging by the answers of the subjects, it is clear that they do not understand why they want to write like this, which violates their everyday reality. : “good evening, why such questions, I'm shocked...” or “ahahaha what did I find on you?..” The answers of these respondents completely misunderstood why the information was written in this language. This shows that the experimenter violated both the rules of Internet communication and the everyday reality of the subject. They make various assumptions, and the sender can send them such a message based on these assumptions : “ты что, пьян?))” Messages vary in size. For example, the majority of respondents responded to text messages in this way: “everything is fine Barno, with your prayers..” or “hi, everything is fine, here, I'm looking for a job..”

The full answers came like this:

“Good evening, Barno. Things are not bad so far, there is nothing much to tell. I hope you are satisfied with the answer?! I'm no less interested in how your life is going. I'll be waiting for an answer from you..” or:

“Hello, my dear. Unfortunately, it takes a lot of time to work and to write a term paper. I'm on my way home from work now, when will we finally meet you? With love, Liana . . .

Therefore, we can say that these subjects have adopted the way of giving them information, and therefore in their answers they consciously adopted "new rules of the game". This shows that the new form of speech has a certain degree of flexibility. Most of the messages received contain so-called "emoticons". It takes the form of brackets ")" or emoticons attached to the Facebook app itself, as shown below :

"ahhahaha what?)." or "Hi,ahaha, what's wrong with you Bonnie?))Everything is fine, how are you doing?)) I finish, at the end of June, I will receive a second specialty) How are you studying?)"

Therefore, we can say that Internet communication does not obey the rules of written language, which means that it has lost its way of expression. This problem lies in the invention of "emoticons" that express a person's emotions not in words, but in pictures. In the end, putting a "smiley face" is much easier and faster than drawing tell me how you feel.

The narrative language is similar to the literary language in the following information :

"Hello, my dear. Unfortunately, it takes a lot of time to work and to write a term paper. I'm on my way home from work now, when will we finally meet you? With love, Liana. . ."

The full answers came like this:

"Good evening, Barno. Things are not bad so far, there is nothing much to tell. I hope you are satisfied with the answer?! I'm no less interested in how your life is going. I will wait for an answer from you.."

From the data obtained, it can be concluded that the subjects regarded this as a joke and began to use a form of humor in response. This may be due to the fact that the literary language is not implemented in virtual communication. Text fragmentation was observed in some messages. for example :

"My dear Bonnie

Here it is

Awesome

I have an ex tomorrow

I'm getting ready and sitting

Let's call tomorrow I have something to tell you. . ."

Thus, we see that the answer of only one respondent was similar to the literary language. We see a misunderstanding of the situation in almost half of the messages. Probably, the misunderstanding occurred for the reason that the social network is a place where communication takes place in a different form, in which it is not customary to write in literary language. In general, we can say that most of the messages were characteristic of the social

network signs: fragmentary, the presence of emoticons, abbreviations of words, an abundance of inappropriate punctuation marks and a lack of “correct” signs.

According to the results of the interview, we saw that all respondents use Internet buzzwords in virtual communication, and quite often. They shorten words, mainly for the purpose of quickly writing a message:

“well, in order to write faster, I save time..” or “yes, it happens that you need to write somewhere faster, I know that my interlocutor will understand me, so I shorten..”

Some respondents believe that punctuation is not important in Internet communication, for example: "Well, in my opinion, you can use several emoticons to express your whole idea, and punctuation is no longer relevant. "The majority of respondents believe that online slang will block the language and reduce the level of language and culture. “Well, because these short meaningless words are more popular, while ordinary words are forgotten and retreated behind the scenes. "Or “I think so because it's all come into real life.”

Respondents believe that it is acceptable to use online slang in everyday speech, but not everyone can : “Well, not with everyone, . in my circle” or “Well, yes, I think, but again, it should be in certain some such, in a certain communication.”

Thus, we saw that all respondents used slang expressions. Moreover, this is true not only in virtual communication, but also in their everyday colloquial speech. It can be concluded that online slang has a serious impact on the vocabulary of the younger generation, since it is used in almost all types of speech activity of young people. These customs are so ingrained in the daily lives of young people that they consider them a “part of everyday life” and an acceptable way of expressing themselves in their speeches.

Consequently, it can be concluded that young people often use online slang interpreted as “popular”, “This is the language of youth”. The deep-rooted nature of this expression can be seen by the frequency of use of these words and the content of virtual communication and oral speech. Thus, we see that there is a process of “overflowing” of virtual words into the everyday spoken language of young people. In addition, according to the respondents' responses, it can be said that young people consider slang as a “given” and “part of everyday life”, but believe that it reduces the level of language and culture to a certain extent.

In general, based on the results of a sociological study, we can say: first of all, we can see the reaction of young people to the written literary form of the language addressed to them and find out why this happens.

We learned that the Internet, especially social networks, is a special medium of communication, and the literary language was not reflected. Online speech is a new form of language that now exists not only in writing, but also in oral form. By calling a young person a literary language on social networks, we thus violate the everyday reality in which he often lives accordingly.

This is the reaction we received, which makes people misunderstand why the recipient wrote to him in this way, and not in other ways. For those respondents whose information is close to the form of literary language, we can say that they simply accepted the rules of the “new game”, nothing more.

Secondly, we learned that young people not only actively use online slang in online communication, but are also very active in everyday colloquial speech. It is not difficult for informants to interpret fashionable Internet buzzwords. We also managed to find out the relationship between the modern younger generation and slang expressions. Some respondents agreed that the use of slang in everyday speech is acceptable. Many people agree that slang expressions reduce the level of language and culture. Thus, online slang is a deeply rooted form of youth use not only in virtual communication, but also in everyday speech, it has its own unique structure and characteristics that are inherent only in this method of communication.

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